

Medicinal Plants from Democratic Republic of the Congo as Sources of Anticancer Drugs

Koto-te-Nyiwa Ngbolua^{1,2,*}, Damien S. Tshibangu², Pius T. Mpiana², Virima Mudogo², Dorothée D. Tshilanda², Colette Masengo Ashande¹, Selvaraj Divakar³, Muthiah Ramanathan³, Govindarajan Syamala³

¹University of Gbadolite, P.O. Box 111 Gbadolite, Nord-Ubangi Province, Democratic Republic of the Congo

²Faculty of Science, University of Kinshasa, P.O. Box 190 Kinshasa XI, Democratic Republic of the Congo

³Department of Pharmacology, PSG College of Pharmacy, Coimbatore, India

*Corresponding author: Koto-te-Nyiwa Ngbolua, Ph: +243 81 68 79 527, E-mail: jpngbolua@unikin.ac.cd

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ABSTRACT:

According to the WHO, more than 80% of the population in Africa resort to the traditional medicine for their health care. In the present study, a survey was carried out among traditional practitioners and the most cited plant species was submitted to anticancer experiments *in vitro*. The results revealed that *Gardenia ternifolia* contains secondary metabolites with anticancer activity and is selective towards breast (MCF-7) cancerous cell lines.

Keyword: Evidence based Medicine, indigenous knowledge, botanical Medicine, cancer, DR Congo.

INTRODUCTION

Cancer is a major public health problem all over the world and constitutes the second leading cause of death after cardiovascular disease [1]. Because of serious side effects of both chemo- and radiation therapies, many patients seek alternative and complementary methods of treatment. Several anti-cancer agents derived from plant species (Taxol, Camptothecin, Topotecan, etc. and their derivatives) are in clinical use or in preclinical development (Flavopiridol, Silvestrol, Betulinic acid, etc.) [2]. Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) as one of the hotspots of plant biodiversity in the world could play a key role in the R & D of new anti-cancer agents from its flora [3]. The aims of this multidisciplinary research program were: (a) To validate scientifically the traditional use of selected plant species by investigating anti-cancer activity of their extracts as a possible source of anti-cancer hits using human prostate (PC-3) and breast (MCF-7) cancerous cell lines and non-cancerous rat skeletal muscle L6 cell lines as model systems (Scientific evidence based Traditional Medicine); (b) To evaluate the therapeutic index of the biologically active extracts; (c) To develop anti-cancer phytomedicines as a result of the transformation of indigenous/ethno-medical knowledge into large scale action by the mean of Science and Technology (Research for sustainable development).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

An ethno-botanical survey was conducted in DRC according to the principles laid out in the Declaration of Helsinki and the Nagoya protocol. Traditional Healers and/or medicinal plant vendors (50) were interviewed about medicinal plants used in Congolese folk medicine [4]. The powdered leaves of *Gardenia ternifolia* were extracted by maceration. Successive extractions were carried out with organic solvents of increasing polarity (Petroleum ether, Chloroform, Ethyl acetate, Methanol and Methanol 80%). Anti-cancer bioactivity of different extracts was assessed by MTT assay. Paclitaxel was used as positive control [5].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ethno-botanical survey revealed that the most cited plant species was *Gardenia ternifolia* (or Lembanzau in Kikongo) with a high value of informant consensus factor (0.361). Biological screening revealed that chloroform and ethyl acetate soluble fractions are biologically active against MCF-7 cell lines with a CC50 (50% cytotoxic concentration) of $21.62 \pm 1.6 \mu\text{g/mL}$ and $45.44 \pm 2.2 \mu\text{g/mL}$ respectively. For PC-3 cell lines, the CC50 were $9.66 \pm 2.6 \mu\text{g/mL}$ and $24.47 \pm 1.1 \mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively for chloroform and ethyl acetate extracts. The petroleum ether, methanol and methanol 80% crude extracts were inactive against both MCF-7 and PC-3 cell lines ($50 < \text{CC50} < 100$ or $\text{CC50} > 100 \mu\text{g/mL}$). The chloroform extract displayed interesting therapeutic index or safety ratio ($\text{CC50 L6/CC50 MCF-7}$ or $\text{PC-3} \geq 3$). This extract is 3 or 7 times selective in killing the cancerous cell lines (MCF-7 or PC-3) than the non-cancerous cell lines (L6) [5]. This could be due to the different secondary metabolites extracted with the chloroform solvent.

Figure 1 : *Gardenia ternifolia*

CONCLUSION

The chloroform extract of *Gardenia ternifolia* decreases the cancerous cell lines density in vitro. As potential candidate, *G. ternifolia* could be developed as therapeutic phytomedicine against human prostate and breast cancers. Further studies are therefore in progress to purify and elucidate the structure(s) of bioactive compounds.

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